

THE STRUCTURAL RELATIONSHIP PATTERN BETWEEN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' INTRINSIC MOTIVATION, EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION AND ATTITUDESⁱ

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Abstract:

The purpose of the present study is to identify the structural relationship pattern among intrinsic, extrinsic motivation and attitudes. For this aim, the Academic Motivation Scale and The Attitude Questionnaire for English Course were administered to a total of 631 university students in order to identify their motivational types together with levels and their attitudes towards learning. The data were analysed through Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). At the end of the research, the structural model framed upon the variables was tested, analysed and verified within the recommended values of fit indices. The results of the study suggested that the correlation value between students' extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation ($r=.26$); attitude and intrinsic motivation ($r=.25$); as well as attitude and extrinsic motivation ($r=.39$) are all positive and significant (Critical Ratio = 4.57, $p < .05$; Critical Ratio = 5.81, $p < .05$; Critical Ratio = 5.30, $p < .05$ respectively). Correspondent with the findings of the study, some recommendations and implications were made to consider to promote the motivation and positive attitudes.

Keywords: self-determination theory, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, attitudes

1. Introduction

Gömleksiz and Kan (2012) argue that the primary requirement of keeping up with the incredible transformation and development in today's societies is "being equipped" against life, and that only "cognitively" competent people cannot have satisfactory results in any way. Accordingly, such a situation will only serve for people to be overwhelmed with the burden of piles of knowledge. Therefore, it will be possible to become equipped against the requirements of the age only if the affective and cognitive domains are sufficiently covered and improved. In this regard, Martin and Reigeluth (1999) state that

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with the advent of the industrial age, the educational programs required by this age are based solely on cognitive learning; however, with the information age, individuals need affective domain requirements as well as cognitive dimension. The statement of Farley (2001) is quite appealing in this sense: What tomorrow needs is not a mass of intellectuals, but rather a mass of educated people who know how to feel, behave and think in different and creative ways.

In this sense, motivation has a very significant place in affective domain and is considered as an important notion that attracts attention in the education (Parker and Engel, 2001; Kassae and Rowell, 2016). Deriving from the Latin “movere”, motivation is generally defined as, in its most general form, the individuals’ own intentions to behave in a variety of ways to achieve a specific purpose (Baumeister and Vohs, 2007); a general concept that includes desires, needs, impulses and interests (Cüceloğlu, 2004); the driving force that activates the organism, energizes, causes an emotional rise and directs the behaviours in order to achieve certain goals and the necessary behaviours (Fidan, 1996) and the inner desires that individuals exhibit or possess in acquiring or learning new information (Lin, 2012). Dörnyei’s (1994) definition of motivation is related to the feeling of excitement or arousal that develops internally and shows a cumulative characteristic. Although motivation has been evaluated in a single structure for a long time, Ryan and Deci (2000) state that this concept is activated by a wide variety of experiences and results, even in the most superficial definition, with different and somewhat independent factors. From this point of view, Ryan and Deci (2000), in their Self-Determination Theory, have made a distinction between the motivational types of individuals based on different reasons or the reasons behind the realization of any action. Self-Determination Theory, which is one of the most effective and detailed theories explaining the motivation of individuals (Lee, 2011; Dörnyei, 2003), proposes an approach in which motivation is grouped as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The theory itself connotes the idea that the type of the motivation has to be handled and studied rather than the total amount of motivation level (Ryan and Deci, 2008).

Intrinsic motivation is defined as the doing of an activity for its inherent satisfactions rather than some separable consequences by Ryan and Deci (2000). In this sense, intrinsic motivation refers to the self, the actions and behaviours performed by and for the self. These behaviours and actions provide personal satisfaction and pleasure by nature (Little et al., 2002; Gagne and Deci, 2005). In this case, the actions taken by individuals in line with their wishes and expectations provide an internal sense of motivation and ensure the continuity of these behaviour patterns and efforts. In other words, the theory asserts that once individuals intrinsically motivated, they will perform an activity or a given task simply on account of the enjoyment and satisfaction by the activity itself (Ryan and Deci, 2000; Gagne and Deci, 2005; Vallerand, Pelletier, Blais, Biere, Senecal and Valleries, 1992).

Stating that students do homework and research to learn new and interesting things as an example of intrinsic motivation. Within the framework of intrinsic motivation, Vallerand and Ratelle (2002) suggest a three-dimensional construct: intrinsic

motivation to know, intrinsic motivation to accomplish and intrinsic motivation to stimulate. Accordingly, individuals tend to be more intrinsically motivated in the supply and satisfaction of these three psychological needs (Vallerand and Ratelle, 2002; Moreno, 2010; Pelletier, 2002).

On the other hand, Self-Determination Theory also states that human behaviour is not always shaped by intrinsic motivation. Ideally, individuals move by nature to meet their needs such as autonomy, social relationship and competence. However, in some cases, human behaviour is often shaped by pressure, control, and coercion apart from the self. In these cases, individuals are exposed to extrinsic motivation (Vallerand and Ratelle, 2002; Kasser, 2002). In other words, extrinsic motivation is confronted when an individual performs an activity or a given task for the sake of the reasons outside the activity itself. Therefore, in such actions where motivation is considered as a tool, reinforcements such as reward, feedback, praise, acceptance, and feeling proud can be guiding. Participation of the students in the course activities in order to pass the exams and to make their parents happy are examples of extrinsic motivation (Gagne and Deci, 2005; Moreno, 2010; Schunk, 2011).

In many studies, intrinsic motivation is given more emphasis than extrinsic motivation and these studies highlight that intrinsic motivation provides higher academic success in learning process (Rogers, 2012; Areepattamannil, Freeman and Klinger, 2011; Wu, 2003; Ayub, 2010; Moreno, 2010). It also increases the important skills such as creativity (Amabile, 1985), and makes individuals spend more time in the learning process (Cordova and Lepper, 1996). The point that is emphasized here is the fact that the intrinsic motivation outruns the extrinsic motivation in which the reinforcements taken from outside gain importance and the individuals concentrate on these reinforcements rather than their actions in the learning process (Lee, 2011).

The concept of attitude, which is another important component of affective domain, has become one of the basic concepts discussed with the beginning of systematic studies in the field of educational psychology. In general, the term attitude is understood as an element of evaluation and, accordingly, the concept can be defined as the reaction of individuals to the events, objects or situations they face in structuring the complex environment. Therefore, attitudes can be expressed in the form of particles of social knowledge consisting of experiences, beliefs and emotions. (Basadur and Basadur, 2011). In other words, attitudes are internal phenomena that shape personal movements and consist of individual characteristics such as commitment to life, living a healthy life, honour, righteousness, conscience and empathy. Unlike cognitive domain characteristics, like other affective domain characteristics, attitudes cannot be directly measured and observed. The act of determining attitudes can only take place indirectly. Similar to personality, attitude is a concept that cannot be measured directly but can be deduced by measurable reactions. Schunk, (2011) states that attitudes are learned indirectly through experiences and through observation of live or symbolic examples. Due to the nature of the structure in question, these reactions include positive or negative evaluations of a situation, an event or an object (Icek, 2005; Bernd and Schwarz, 2007).

To conclude, the concept of attitude is defined as the response of individuals to the events, objects or situations they face and is described as an element of evaluation (Basadur and Basadur, 2011). Gardner (1978) states that academic achievement, especially during the acquisition of basic language skills, is largely determined by the attitudes towards the language learned, and argues that attitude is roughly an emotional trait and complementary to the concept of motivation in the language learning process. Similarly, many researchers found that positively developed attitude mostly correlate with higher levels of motivation (Bidin et al. 2009; Ming, Ling and Jaafar, 2011; Altnok, 2004; Akandere, Özyalvaç and Duman, 2010).

In the light of the theoretical framework and empirical findings, it is thought that the results obtained from this study will contribute to better understanding of the structural relationships between motivational types, namely intrinsic and extrinsic, and attitudes. In addition, the results of the research are also thought to be useful in the planning, implementation and evaluation stages of education and training programs.

From this point of view, the following research question formed the purpose of the present study:

- What is the structural the relationship pattern between intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and attitudes among university students?

2. Material and Method

2.1 Research Design

The causal research design was applied in this study, which investigate the cause and effect relationship patterns among the variables.

2.2 Participants

The study group of the study consisted of students attending a state university in İstanbul, Turkey, in 2013-2014 academic year. The study group initially consisted of 654 students, but 23 questionnaires were ignored and the final number of the group was determined as 631. Gender distribution of the students in the study group is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Gender Distribution of the Study Group

Gender	F	%
Female	224	35.5
Male	407	64.5
Total	631	100

In Table 1, it seen that, a total of 631 the participants formed the study group and 224 of them are female (35.5%) and 407 of them are male (64.5) students.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

2.3.1 The Academic Motivation Scale

In order to determine the motivational levels of the students, the Academic Motivation Scale, which was developed by Vallerand et al. (1992) was applied to the participants. The scale was adapted into Turkish by Karataş and Erden (2012) and it has three sub-scales which assess the types of motivation: intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and amotivation.

The Academic Motivation Scale was applied to Turkish university students and the internal consistency coefficient was found .97 Cronbach Alpha. The factor analysis results indicated that that the factors explain 68.59 % of the total variance in the scale (Karataş and Erden, 2012).

2.3.1 The Attitude Questionnaire for English Course

In order to determine the attitudes of students towards English, Attitude Questionnaire for English Course was used. The original version of the questionnaire was developed by Aiken (1979) and translated into Turkish by Tunç (2003) and adapted to determine attitudes towards English. The internal consistency coefficient of the questionnaire was calculated .88 Cronbach Alpha.

2.4 Data Analysis

The data obtained from the study were analysed with Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). SEM is defined as the statistical method used to determine the relationship between one or more independent variables and one or more dependent variables. In addition, this method can be used to test, analyse and reveal the multidimensional structure of any model (Ullman and Bentler, 2013).

3. Results

The model below demonstrates the structural relationship pattern among intrinsic, extrinsic motivation and attitude.

In Figure 1, the statistical values among the variables in terms of the structural relationship pattern are displayed. The above model was analysed with maximum likelihood method in AMOS software program. In order to use this method and to reach the correct results, it is necessary to use a set of indices required by the system. The values of these indices are very important in terms of revealing and analysing the compatibility between the model and the data obtained (Bayram, 2013).

Figure 1: The Structural Relationship Pattern Values among the Variables

The common indices used in Structural Equation Modelling are illustrated in Table 2 and these indices are Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Relative Fit Index, (RFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) (Weston and Gore, 2006; Çokluk, Şekercioğlu and Büyüköztürk, 2012; Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003; Ullman and Bentler, 2013).

Table 2: Recommendation of Model Evaluation and the Values of the Analyzed Model

Fit Indices	Good Fit	Acceptable Fit	The Values of the Model
χ^2/df	$.0 \leq \chi^2/df \leq 2$	$2 \leq \chi^2/df \leq 3$	2.4
RMSEA	$0 \leq RMSEA \leq .05$	$0 \leq RMSEA \leq .08$	.07
NFI	$.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$.90 \leq NFI \leq .95$	.91
CFI	$.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$.95 \leq CFI \leq .97$	.96
GFI	$.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	$.90 \leq AGFI \leq .95$	.91
AGFI	$.90 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$	$.85 \leq AGFI \leq .90$	.87

(Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003).

Table 2 shows the fit index values obtained from the model. Accordingly, the Chi-Square value which is calculated by dividing the degree of freedom has been found 2.4 ($.0 \leq \chi^2/df \leq 3$); Normed Fit Index (NFI) value .91 ($.90 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$); Comparative Fit Index (CFI) value .96 ($.95 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$); The Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI) was .91 ($.90 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$) and the Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit-Index (AGFI) was .87 ($.85 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$). These values are within the conformity reference values and are considered as good indicators of compatibility of the model. In addition, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) value, which should be in the $0 \leq RMSEA \leq .08$ range, was found .07. In the light of these data, it can be concluded that the suitability of the model is significant, and that the data are within the reference value ranges.

In Table 3, the correlations, standard errors, critical ratios and 'p' values of the model's variables are listed.

Table 3: The Correlations, standard errors, critical ratios and 'p' values of the model's variables

Correlations	Correlation Value	Standard Error	Critical Ratios	p Values
Extr. Mot. ↔ Intr. Mot.	.26	0.75	4.57	.00**
Attitude ↔ Intr. Mot.	.25	0.43	5.81	.00**
Attitude ↔ Extr. Mot.	.39	0.68	5.30	.00**

**p < .05

In Table 3, the correlations, standard errors, critical ratios and "p" values of the variables of the model are itemized. When the table is examined, it is seen that the correlation value between students' extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation is $r=.26$; attitude and intrinsic motivation is $r=.25$; as well as attitude and extrinsic motivation is $r=.39$. The "p" value between the two variables (.00) demonstrates that the correlations are positive and significant (Critical Ratio = 4.57, $p < .05$; Critical Ratio = 5.81, $p < .05$; Critical Ratio = 5.30, $p < .05$).

5. Discussion and Conclusions

When the findings of the present study are evaluated and taken as a whole, it can be concluded that the university students' attitudes and the motivation types they have (intrinsic and extrinsic motivation) play a significant and positive impact on their academic achievement.

In this sense, among the affective variables that have profound impact on the process of learning, variables such as motivation and attitude, which include the factors that activate and direct the behaviour, are often seen as the main reasons for success and failure (Gardner, 1985; Rifai, 2010). In fact, Scovel (1978) states that there is no need to examine the literature in detail to reveal the relationship between language learning and affective factors, and that there is a clear relationship between the concepts. The findings of the present study are in line with many studies, highlighting that positive attitude and motivation increase academic achievement; on the other hand, negative attitude or low motivation level is associated with failure (Mcgeown, Norgate and Warhurst, 2012;

Emmett, 2013; Akandere, Özyalvaç and Duman, 2010; Bernaus, Wilson and Gardner, 2009; Yu, 2010; MacIntyre, Potter and Burns, 2012; Allen and Herron, 2003; Çelebi, 2009). As a consequence, it can be argued that motivation and attitude are of undeniable importance in the process of learning since, as stated, it is impossible to separate motivation and learning in the application areas and it is not an easy task for students to learn without motivation. Since it can affect learning positively in many ways, it is necessary to evaluate the motivational effects of educational practices and classroom activities along with finding convenient ways to promote positive attitudes in learning environments.

Therefore, determining the roles and levels of these factors at every stage of learning and shaping the planning process in the light of the results will positively affect the academic achievement of the students. In addition, in order to increase students' interest and attention to the school atmosphere as well as the learning process, decision-makers, planners and teachers should be aware that affective factors are as important as cognitive factors. For this purpose, it is thought that affective factors should be processed effectively in order to obtain more satisfactory academic results in the development of education and training programs.

The model analysed in this study depends on the data that have been gained from the freshman students. It is suggested that the same model should be investigated in different studies to be conducted on students attending different programs and classes. Further, the results obtained from the research were obtained in the 13th and 14th weeks, towards the end of the first term of the academic year. Since it is thought that the attitudes and behaviours of the students towards the school are likely to change due to various reasons such as institutions, courses, environmental factors, exams, teachers and peer groups in the course of time, it is important that the researchers conduct the data collection tools either at the beginning or at the end of the academic year.

About the Author

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